

Reliability Index of Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) for Assessing Learning Approaches of Nigerian University Education Students

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Abstract

This research assessed reliability index of revised two-factor study process questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) among Nigerian university education students. Ex post facto design was used. The study used 101 students as samples drawn from the university. The Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) was adopted to measure learning approaches and analysis of the Cronbach's Alpha and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical tools were used to get the index level of reliability of R-SPQ-2F. One hypothesis was formulated and tested. The analysis revealed that this instrument scored .77 on Cronbach Alpha levels, which displayed a very high positive relationship and the result of the analysis of PPMC index level of reliability of R-SPQ-2F was .626, which indicates a high positive relationship as well.

Keywords: learning approaches, reliability index, Cronbach's Alpha, Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Introduction

University education in Nigeria has nowadays becomes the yearnings and aspirations of our teeming young men and women in the country. These youth will come into the university environment with varying motives and strategies about learning at the university level. There emerged the need to study how and why students at higher institution of learning came to study. Many scholars have delved into developing instruments to monitor students' learning at this level. These include Approaches to Study Inventory (ASI) by (Entwistle & Ramsden, 1983) Learning and Study Strategies Inventory by Weinstein, Schult, & Palmer, (1987) Study Process Questionnaire by Biggs (1987) and Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) was later developed by Biggs, Kember, & Leung (2001).

The study on how students approach their learning has just begun in Nigeria, using the concepts: *deep* approach and *surface* approach to learning. This theory which begun in Europe, has found wider acceptance and usage in Asia. Marton and Säljö (1976) was the pioneer of the study of students learning approaches in higher education. These scholars worked on how and why students engage in learning at the University of Gotenburg, Sweden, and came to discover that there were two categories of approaches students adopt in their studies, namely, *deep* approach and *surface* approach. That is to say, Marton and Säljö (1976a & 1976b) came up with the idea of "approach to learning", which became the point of departure and therefore the emerging conceptual framework known generically as "student approaches to learning" (SAL) theory (Biggs, 1993a; Entwistle & Waterston, 1988). SAL theory has in fact become a meta-theory for conceptualizing teaching and learning, which has gone in two major directions: phenomenography (Marton, 1981; Prosser & Trigwell, 1998) and constructivism and systems theory (Biggs, 1999; Dart & Boulton-Lewis, 1998). The questionnaire was also developed before the insights into approaches to learning gained from the intensive study of the approaches of Asian students (Kember, 1996; Watkins & Biggs, 1996). For this simple two-factor version of the SPQ the intention was not to develop scales which fully characterized the possible combinations of understanding and memorizing. The work, though, was utilized to ensure that the deep and surface approach items were consistent with the clearer descriptions which had emerged from this body of work. It was on these concepts many higher education researchers built on in their studies. Several scholars have established that the learning approach adopted by a student is related to the quality of his learning outcome (Subasinghe and Wanniachchi, 2013 and Valadas, 2013).

Negash, Eshete and Hanago (2022) stated that, learning approaches are strategies applied to learning that are critical to success, considered essential for acquiring good grades, and useful for learning throughout one's life. According to Mel (2021), deep learning is a committed approach to learning where the learner uses higher-order cognitive skills to master

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academic content, work collaboratively and think and interact critically and actively with the content being learned. While surface learning is more concern with passing the course with little effort, and many times engage in memorization of learning material. Sagar (2020) put forth that, the deep learning approach encourages learners to think critically, understand meaning and can apply what they learn to new situations and contexts. In addition, Amadi and Ironanya (2020) also stated that the essence of deep learning understands true knowing. However, for surface learning, learners tend to avoid the hard work and instead rely on single source of information, and as a result, they learn only what is required but nothing more (Biggs 1999 in Mel, 2021), (Hussin, Hamed and Jam 2017). Furthermore, the surface learning is a rather passive approach to learning where students scraping the surface of the material being studied and concentrating only on the assessment requirements without getting into the details, with the only intention of passing the exams or test (Mel, 2021). Meanwhile, Pute, Abdul-Latif, Mansor and Halid (2018) also stated that a student using a surface approach only intended to capture contents in total, rather than understand it thoroughly.

According to D'cruzand, Rajaratnam (2018) pointed out that, the surface learning approach is memorizing, syllabus-bound, and exam-oriented, whereas the deep approach to learning is seeking for meaning, relating ideas, and using evidence in learning. While Brown, White, Wakeling and Naiker (2015) stated that, a deep approach to learning can help students to understand the concept and improve their academic performance. Students may follow the surface learning approach due to fear of failure, stress, and lack of purpose.

The surface approach is totally in distinction with the deep approach. Therefore, it is important for the educators to understand the different ways how the students learn and interpret. Understanding the learner types among our students is very important in helping and guiding them in their more meaningful learning process. This is because of the learning approaches will influence the academic attainment. According to Cetin and Mart (2016), the massive gaps between deep and surface approaches have been consistently established across a large variety of qualitative and quantitative studies in numerous countries and study fields through diverse testing methods. Learning approaches have been linked to the performance of students' learning outcomes, which may depend to the evaluation approach used. Desierto, Maio, Rourke and Edith (2019) put forth that, in moving from surface to deep learning strategies, students can alternate between both learning approaches depending on their academic tasks or when struggling with their workloads.

A sample of health science students from a university in Hong Kong were asked to complete the questionnaire. A total of 229 usable questionnaires were returned, with a high return rate since the questionnaires were handed out for completion in class. The Cronbach alpha values are 0.73 for Deep Approach and 0.64 for Surface Approach in the sample, which are considered as acceptable.

Negash, Eshete and Hanago (2022) conducted research on Students' learning approaches as a factor of academic achievement at selected public universities: A cross-sectional study a cross-sectional study was conducted on 123 anesthesia students. All 3rd- and 4th-year students were recruited for the study. Approaches to Study Skills Inventory for Students (ASSIST) were used to assess students' learning approaches. Perceived performance, cumulative grade point average (CGPA), and 100 Multiple Choice Questions items were used to assess academic achievement. Data were entered into Epi-data and exported to SPSS for statistical analysis. An independent *t*-test was used to determine the presence of a difference in academic achievement across learning approaches. Bivariate and multivariable linear regressions were fitted to assess the association of students' characteristics and learning approaches with their academic achievement. A *P*-value of less than 0.05 was used to declare the statistical significance.

Gurjiya (2021) conducted an investigation on gender disparity in learning approaches and academic performance among Colleges of Education students in Katsina state. The researcher used 333 students as samples drawn from three tertiary institutions. The study did not find any significant difference in the academic performance of male deep learners and female deep learners' approach. So also, the study did not find any significant difference in the academic performance of male surface learners and female surface learners.

Roslandb and Abdullah (2021) examined students' intention to engage in deep learning with the aim to understand them better. According to their finding, majority of students practice surface learning approach. They used Theory of Planned Behavior, where they related the components of the theory with main quest of students' intention to engage in deep learning, where the attainable predictors are students' attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control. Online survey was conducted and analyzed both statistically and descriptively, revealed that students are deep learners. The model was also found significant, with all three predictors were positive and significantly contributing to students' intention to engage in deep learning. Nonetheless, detailed analysis suggests that none of the predictors appeared to have a stronger effect over the others.

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The findings from their study confirm the applicability of the Theory of Planned Behavior in explaining students' intention to engage in deep learning.

Samosa (2021) investigated on Cooperative Learning Approach as Innovation to Improve Students' Academic Achievement and Attitude in Teaching Biology. The study sought to determine the effectiveness of cooperative learning approach against conventional teaching. The study employed the experimental type of research. The design compared the result obtained from researcher – made - achievement test and attitude survey in biology in experimental sample which is cooperative learning approach with the control sample exposed to Direct Instruction. The study revealed that the gained scores of the experimental group gained 41.86 % from the pre- and post-achievement test greater than the controlled group gained score of 36.49 %. Furthermore, in the attitude survey showed that the experimental group gained 81.90 % from the pre- and post-attitude survey which was greater than the control group gained 81.69%. Using t- test of significance in both control group and experimental group showed that there is no significance difference between pre – achievement test and post – achievement test at probability level of greater than 0.05. In F -test revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre-attitude score and post- attitude score of the control and experimental groups.

Mel (2021) conducted study on Deep versus Surface Learning: A Study among Thermodynamics Students in Politeknik Kuching Sarawak, Malaysia. The study showed that deep learning approach was the most dominant learning approach used by the students. Then, the study also showed that the deep learning approach had positive correlation with academic attainment while the surface learning approach was inversely proportional with academic attainment. Therefore, students are encouraging to become a deep learner rather than surface learner. Furthermore, the study also revealed that the significant of educators to teach awareness to the students on the different approaches in their learning. Thus, by promoting or inducing the deep learning approach among students, it is hope that the surface approach to learning can be minimized. Educators also need to be aware that their teaching practices can affect the intention of the students to learning too.

The two broad learning approaches, deep and surface have consistently emerged through research in this area. Students' learning approaches are particularly important to teachers because they are not fixed traits and are susceptible to outside influences, especially the learning environment, teaching methods and assessment tools. With knowledge of strategies, which encourage deep learning and surface learning by teachers, students' learning at higher level of education will be improved. This paper investigated the reliability index of Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) learning approach instrument among Nigerian university education students of Sule Lamido University, Kafin Hausa, Jigawa State, North West, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to assess whether Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) is a reliable instrument for assessing learning approach among Nigerian university education students.

Hypothesis

Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) is not a reliable instrument for assessing learning approach among Nigerian university education students.

Methodology

Data about students' learning approaches was obtained via Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) developed by Biggs, Kember and Leung (2001). The instrument used in the study was the 20-item revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) developed by Biggs, Kember and Leung (2001) which had a reliability index of .66 was adopted. It has two sections: Section A contains personal information of the participants and Section B contains the 20-item 5-Point Likert Statements loaded with deep/surface learning approaches.

The sample of the study was 101 education students drawn from Sule Lamido University, Kafin Hausa, Jigawa State, North-West, Nigeria. The researcher used one day in the institution to administer the questionnaire with the assistance of the lecturer holding lectures at the time of the visit. The subjects were then requested to fill in and submit the questionnaire there and then. The data collected were at the interval and the hypothesis was tested using Cronbach's Alpha and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistics.

Results

Hypothesis Testing

Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) is not a reliable instrument for assessing learning approaches of Nigerian university education students.

Table 1: Analysis of the Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Statistics of R-SPQ-2F (N = 101)

VV Cronbach's Alpha	Nn	N of Items
...7 .770	222	2

Table 1 presents the result of analysis of the Cronbach's Alpha index level of reliability of R-SPQ-2F. The analysis revealed that the instrument scored .77 Alpha levels, which displayed a very high reliability index. This has invariably indicated that the instrument is reliable in identifying both the deep and surface variables among university students given the Alpha level the instrument scored.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the study revealed that Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) is a reliable instrument for assessing learning approaches of Nigerian university education students. In order words, the instrument has been found to have good items that can fish out deep learners and surface learners among students. The result is concurrent with that of Gurjiya (2015), Biggs, Kember, & Leung, (2001), who also reported a significant relationship in learning approach between deep learning approach sub-scale and surface learning approach. The students have now understood the expectation of the learning environment and the assessment tools being in use by the teachers in the university. Where a course requires one to use deep approach or surface approach, the students were quick at switching to the mode that gives greater advantage of getting higher grades.

Conclusion

The study concludes that Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) has an index of .77 hence, is a reliable instrument for assessing learning approaches of university education students in Nigerian.

Recommendation

The Revised Two Factors study process questionnaire should be employed by teachers as a tool for evaluating classroom instructions and researching on students' learning approaches.

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